

Table S4. Summary of GLM with poisson distributed errors, testing the relationship between the species richness and the asynchrony, using the net primary productivity and the topographic heterogeneity as covariates. RAC: spatial effect. df=123

	Estimate	Std.Error	z value	Pr(> z)
Asynchrony	0,039	0,054	0,730	4,666E-01
Productivity	0,891	0,062	14,418	< 2E-16
Heterogeneity	0,348	0,053	6,516	1,990E-09
Intercept	-0,290	0,090	-3,237	1,580E-03
fitted(RAC-vec7)	-0,803	0,238	-3,371	1,021E-03
fitted(RAC-vec5)	-0,804	0,231	-3,483	7,030E-04
fitted(RAC-vec6)	0,764	0,224	3,405	9,110E-04
fitted(RAC-vec9)	0,712	0,228	3,120	2,284E-03
fitted(RAC-vec1)	0,547	0,237	2,308	2,279E-02